

SYNCRETISM OF SYNTACTICAL RELATIONS IN UZBEK COMPLEX SENTENCES

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Introduction. It should be noted that syntactical relations can be implied as a tool of conjunctions which serves to combine two simple sentences and create one complex. Syncretism of syntactical relations in complex sentences investigates and unites the interaction of these relations. Syntactical relations can be divided into several types and according to the content of the meaning they are listed as a following:

- Syntactical relation of time
- Syntactical relation of place
- Syntactical relation of result
- Syntactical relation of purpose
- Syntactical relation of cause
- Syntactical relation of condition
- Syntactical relation of comparison

¹ Бабайцева В.В. Место переходных явлений в системе языка (на материале частей речи) //

ABSTRACT

The phenomenon of syncretism is described differently in various fields and signifies several functions. One of these functions of syncretism is to combine grammatical units and syntactic relations. Syntactic relations means the connection of distinct clauses in the sentences with the help of coordination, subordination and intonation; predicativeness and non-predicativeness; according to the content of the meaning: the relations of cause, time, purpose, condition, result, place, etc. In this article below we will analyze the syncretism of Uzbek complex sentences and their syntactic relations.

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Literature review. The theoretical basis of the research relies on the fundamental theories of transitivity and syncretism which were deeply studied by V.V. Babaitseva, V.N. Migirin, V.I. Kodukhov and others. Also, the works dedicated to syncretic linguistic phenomena were published by S.A.Aleksanova, I.V. Artyushkov, V.V. Babaitseva, A. Ya. Bauder, L.D. Bednarskaya, I.V. Vysotskaya, , PV Chesnokov, L D. Chesnokova, K.E. Stein et al. Structural-semantic classifications of compound sentences N.S. Pospelov, V.A. Beloshapkova, L.Yu. Maksimov, S.G. Ilyenko, L.D. studied by Bednarskaya.¹

Переходность и синкретизм в языке и речи. -М., 1991.-С. 3-14.

Analysis. “Ba’zilari nimani gapirgan bo’lsa, shuni qog’ozga tushirdim.” in this complex sentence syntactical relations of condition and result can be clearly identified and seen how these two relations syncretize as a whole. In the first clause the word “bo’lsa” expresses condition, while “tushirdim” in the second clause means consequence of the action.

In the sentence given below we can observe syncretism of SR of condition and comparison:

“Razm solib qarasangiz, oppoq chinni laganning ikki chetiga ikkita piyola to’nkarib qo’yilganga o’xshaydi” ushbu ergash gapli qo’shma gapda

- Condition: agar razm solib qarasangiz,
- Comparison: oppoq chinni laganning ikki chetiga ikkita piyola to’nkarib qo’yilganga o’xshaydi.

In the next sentence, we can observe that relations in which the subordinate clause expressing the meaning of the condition is syncretized with the principal clause with the meaning of the result: “Ma’lim ertaga qaytib kelsa, qaysi yuz bilan ko’ziga qarayman!”

In the following sentence, you can notice the syntactic relations of condition, time, and consequence: “Ketidan ishkal chiqsa, prorabnimi, brigadirnimi aybdor qiladi.” Here “Ketidan ishkal chiqsa”- conditional suffix, “prorabnimi, brigadirnimi aybdor qiladi”- result and these two clauses spontaneously syntactically syncretize in one complex sentence. This phenomena can also be seen in the following sentence:

“Gitlarning xotinini cho’ri qilib ishlatmasam, xumordan **chiqmayman!**”

“Tugundagi narsa to’n bilan do’ppi ekanini bilib, yuragim ezildi.” - and in this sentence, with the cause relation and the result (consequence) relations together are combined and syncretized in a complex sentence.

And in the following sentence, suffix -ki forms a compound sentence with an adverbial clause, and expresses the syntactic relation of cause, the principal clause expresses the relation of result: “Alam qiladigan joyi shundaki, siz ulardan xohlaganingizni ajratib ololmaysiz.”

“Dadam har gal gugurt chizganida, mo’ylovi yonib ketmasaydi deb qo’rqaman.”- in this sentence we can see how three syntactical relations interact and syncretize in one sentence.

Dadam **har gal** gugurt chizganida – time
mo’ylovi yonib ketmasaydi deb – cause
qo’rqaman – result

In the following sample we can analyze the combination of time relation with the relation of result creating the phenomena of syncretism: “**Bir marta** Alvasti ko’prikda ajina bormish deganimda, dadam so’kib bergan”.

Bir marta Alvasti ko’prikda ajina bormish deganimda – (when?) time
dadam so’kib bergan.- (what happened?)
result.

“Endi danak chaqish uchun o’rnimdan turmoqchi edim, ammanning ovozi chiqib qoldi.” – when analyzing the sentence, it can be understood that in this sentence, both the goal and the time and result relations are syncretized:

Чесноков П.В. Синкретизм статический и динамический // Языковая деятельность: переходность и синкретизм. - М. - Ставрополь, 2001.-С. 27-30.

Чеснокова Л.Д. Грамматические вопросы как средство анализа предложений // РЯШ, 1978. - № 2 - С. 46-52

When? - Endi turmoqchi edim – time
Why?- danak chaqish uchun – purpose
What happened? – ammamning ovozi chiqib qoldi.- result

We can see the combination of time, goal and result relations in one syntactic device when analyzing the following sentence: “Kimsan akam yettinchini bitirganidan keyin shaharga borib o’qimoqchi edi, bobom yo’l qo’ymadi”.

When? - Kimsan akam yettinchini bitirganidan keyin - time

Why? - Kimsan shaharga borib o’qimoqchi edi - purpose

What happened? - bobom yo’l qo’ymadi”- result

In the following sentence we can determine how the syntactical relations of purpose and place combine and syncretize: “Bola narsa sevina qolsin deb jo’xorining sutlirog’idan tanlab, qo’rga ko’mdim.”

• Bola narsa sevina qolsin deb - (why?)- purpose

• qo’rga ko’mdim – (where?) - place

Discussion. We should note that syncretism is a language phenomena that combines and neutralizes opposite or different syntactical relations putting them together at the same syntagmatic level, it is an irreversible systematic shift and living process accompanying the use of language to the simultaneous use of speech units in the process of language development.

Conclusion. From the examples given above, it can be seen that in the Uzbek language, various relationships can occur together creating syncretism in the sentences of which condition-result and cause-result relationships are the most

common types of syntactic relationships. About the essence and importance of this syntactic relations O'.Q. Yusupov says: “Условно-следственное отношение является одним из коммуникативно важных универсальных смысловых отношений. Будучи разновидностью общей категории казуальности, это отношение близко соприкасается с причинно-результативными отношениями. Условно-следственное отношение состоит из двух частей (концов), первая из которых называется условием, вторая – следствием (в логике они называются “основанием” и “следствием” или же “антецедентом” и “консеквентом”). Если условие представлено явлением А, следствие-явлением Б, то содержание этого отношения такое, что осуществление А приводит, может привести или привело бы к осуществлению Б. Иными словами осуществление Б зависит от осуществления А. Графически это отношение можно представить так: $A \rightarrow B$, где А и Б событие или явление, \rightarrow условно следственное отношение. Условно-следственное отношение обобщено отражает зависимую связь между явлениями объективной действительности или же между воображаемыми явлениями.”²In conclusion we can say that in Uzbek language complex sentences which consist of one independent and one or two subordinate clauses have syntactical relations which interact and combine together and creates syncretism.

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² Yusupov O'.Q-Ma`no, tushuncha konsept va lingvokulturologiya atamalari xususida-Toshkent 2011.-B. 40-50

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